

ON THE APPLICABILITY OF FRACTURE MECHANICS TO SHORT FIBRE COMPOSITES

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Abstract

The use of Fracture Mechanics to evaluate the toughness of Short Fibre Composites is examined. J integral tests for composite materials with ductile matrices appear to work well with certain modifications. The J_c measured is independent of specimen size and type but the slope of the R curve (dJ/da) is not. Increasing the temperature results in changes in dJ/da but not in J_c for the temperature range covered. The effect of specimen thickness and the existence of a plane stress/ plane strain transition is examined. It is postulated that such a transition exists only in composites with brittle matrices.

Introduction

Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics has been used to measure the toughness of Short Fibre Composites for a number of years now, at least in academic circles. In common with all property measurements of short fibre composites, the value of toughness measured depends on the fibre orientation and length distributions. These in turn depend on the moulding conditions and the rheological properties of the melt. Consequently the measured toughness is not a material property but rather a characteristic of the material and the moulding conditions.

Composite specimens with ductile matrices exhibit stable crack growth under all loading conditions and for this reason K_c tests cannot be used. In order to characterize the toughness of these materials the use of J integral tests is required. These tests, although reasonably common in metals, have only recently been applied to polymers [1] and composites [2].

When testing composites with more brittle behaviour using K_c tests problems occur when trying to ascertain minimum size requirements to compute size independent toughness values. Changes in specimen size will result in changes in fibre orientations which may effect the measured toughness more than

the original change in specimen size. Despite this problem it has been shown that Fracture Mechanics can provide a useful basis for measuring the fracture resistance of a composite and the effect of microstructural changes on toughness. The measured toughness has been shown to be independent of crack length, specimen type and width [3].

One remaining area of doubt surrounds the effect of specimen thickness and plane stress / plane strain transitions. Because of the skin / core morphology of a short fibre composite, the fibre orientation distribution changes more rapidly with changes in thickness and so it is difficult to gather evidence on thickness effects alone. By using non - standard specimens and other indirect evidence proposals for the effect of thickness on toughness measurements are made depending on the type of matrix behaviour.

Experimental

Six types of material were used in this study:

- a) 33% glass fibre reinforced untoughened Nylon [Grade A]
- b) 33% glass fibre moderately toughened Nylon [Grade B]
- c) 33% glass fibre well toughened Nylon [Grade C]
- d) 30% glass fibre moderately toughened PET [Grade D]
- e) 30% glass fibre well toughened PET [Grade E]
- f) HDPE sheet 1/2" thick

The composites were supplied by DuPont and received in the form of 10" by 4" end gated injection moulded plaques. The plaque thickness was either 1/4" or 1/2".

Specimens were machined from the plaques with the cracks running in the direction of the melt flow into the mould. Three types of specimen were used for the J Tests

- i) Three point Bend Specimens 20 by 100mm
- ii) Large Compact Tension Specimens 100 by 100mm
- iii) Small Compact Tension Specimens 50 by 50mm

The thickness effect specimens were cut so that the crack was made to run through the thickness of the plaque. In this way, by using the portion of the plaque away from the gate where the fibre orientation does not vary with distance from the gate, it was possible to make specimens in which the fibre orientation did not vary with increasing thickness. These specimens have two main

disadvantages; the crack runs through regions of different fibre orientations and so the toughness is not independent of crack length, and secondly the W (width) dimension is not sufficient for valid tests. The specimens were 100mm by 1/2" and had thickness varying from 3mm to 100 mm.

The materials were tested on a screw driven Instron testing machine with a crosshead speed of 5mm/min. The fracture toughness, K_C , was calculated from the formula

$$K_C = \frac{PY\sqrt{a}}{BW}$$

where

P = Load

Y = Calibration Factor (BS5447)

B = Thickness

W = Width

The J values were calculated from

$$J_C = \frac{\eta U_T}{Bb}$$

where

η = Work Factor

U_T = Deformation Energy

b = Ligament

$\eta = 2$ for bend specimens

$\eta = 2.38$ for Compact Tension specimens ($a/w = 0.5$)

The J tests were of the multiple specimen type. Each specimen was loaded to a predetermined load then unloaded. The specimen was treated with dye penetrant, broken open and the crack length measured.

Results and Discussion

A typical J test result is shown in fig.1. There is no blunting line drawn.

There are two reasons for this. Firstly the use of a global yield stress to calculate a dimension smaller than the characteristic dimension of the microstructure is unjustified, particularly as there are such large differences in the yield stresses of the composite components. Consider the case of the grade B Nylon: the plane strain yield stress in compression was 88 MPa and so the predicted blunting at 5 KJ/m², given from

$$J = 2\sigma_{ys} \Delta a$$

would be 28 μm , a distance little over two fibre widths and much less than the typical fibre length or the distance between the fibres. A uniform blunting of 28 μm is clearly not possible.

Secondly there was no evidence of blunting at the notch tip and data points were recorded with energy absorption but no crack growth.

Fig. 1. Typical J - da Curve

Results for these tests on Nylon (Grade B and C) can be seen in figs. 2 and 3. These show the effect of temperature on the J curves of these two materials. In each case the Jc value does not change with the change in temperature. What does change however is the slope of the curve (i.e. the value of dJ/da). Moreover although the slope of the curve increases with increasing temperature in Grade B it

actually reduces slightly in Grade C. It takes more energy to propagate the crack in the Grade B material at the higher temperature than at the lower temperature but less energy to propagate a crack in the Grade C material at the higher temperature.

Fig 2. J Test Results Nylon Grade B

Fig. 3. J Tests Nylon Grade C

This behaviour can be understood if one examines the fracture surfaces at each temperature (figs. 4 and 5). The moderately toughened grade B is only slightly ductile at room temperature but quite ductile at higher temperatures. This greater ductility at higher temperatures will absorb much more energy than the moderately ductile low temperature behaviour. Conversely the well toughened grade C Nylon is already very ductile at room temperature and is not appreciably more ductile in the composite at the higher temperature. As its yield stress will have dropped with this temperature rise less energy will be used to propagate the crack at the higher temperature.

Fig 4. Fracture Surfaces - Nylon Grade B - +23 and +55 deg C

Fig. 5. Fracture Surfaces -Nylon Grade C- +23 and +55 deg C

Short Fibre Composites, in Kc tests , are relatively insensitive to the initial notching technique provided the initial notch tip radius is smaller than the damage zone around a natural propagating crack [4]. Indeed it has been reported that the use of fatigue precracking rather than notching can actually increase the measured fracture toughness slightly [5]. J tests , however, measuring the initiation toughness , appear to be much more sensitive to the initial notching technique (fig.6). The increase in the initial notch radius from 130 μ m to 1mm results in a 50% increase in the value of Jc. This is a much greater difference than that recorded in Kc tests with these notch tip radii.

Fig. 6. Effect of notch radius on Jc Tests

A number of different tests were performed on different types and sizes of samples (fig.7). The Jc values are unchanged by doubling the specimen size and the slopes of the curves little changed.

Fig. 7. Effect of Specimen Type on J Tests.

The tests on the effect of specimen thickness on fracture toughness were performed on specimens of HDPE and PET [Grade E] of identical dimensions. The thicknesses were varied from 3 mm to 100 mm and in this way specimens of each material were tested in thicknesses that should give plane stress conditions for the thinnest specimen and plane strain for the thickest specimen.

The load deflection curves from the HDPE can be seen in fig.8. Note that the thinnest specimen fails in a ductile manner indicative of plane stress. The thickest specimen failed in a much more brittle manner showing the presence of significant through thickness stresses and restraint. In contrast the load deflection curves from the PET (Fig. 9) show no change in their shape with increasing thickness. There are no signs of increasing through thickness stresses in these curves. There appears to be some mechanism preventing the build up of these stresses.

Fig. 8. Types of Load Deflection Curve HDPE

The toughness values calculated for these experiments were almost constant with increasing thickness both for the HDPE and for the PET. As the width of these samples is too small this is probably an effect of insufficient width rather than sufficient thickness.

The type of mechanism which would cause such an effect is illustrated in fig.10 (4). It is a photograph of a failed single Charpy specimen of armour plating steel. Notice that there are two sets of shear lips on the one specimen. An

inclusion in

Fig. 9. Types of Load Deflection Curve PET Composite

the centre of the specimen has resulted in free surfaces in the centre of the specimen and so the through thickness stresses are reduced to zero at this point. The specimen consequently behaves as if it was two separate specimens. Closer examination of the surface reveals a number of smaller shear lips dotted over the fracture surface. In a short fibre composite with a ductile matrix fibre debonding could take the role of the inclusions in the steel plate, so forming a large number of free surfaces and preventing the build up of large through thickness stresses. As a consequence of this, short fibre composites with ductile matrixes will always fail in a state of plane stress no matter what the specimen size.

Fig. 10. Double Shear Lips in Steel [6]

If this argument were true then such an effect should not be seen in composites with brittle matrices which crack before debonding to any significant extent. Evidence for this can be seen in fig.11. It shows the fracture surface of an untoughened Nylon composite. When loaded there were two audible crack jumps

and their semi-elliptical shape can be seen near the initial notch. The elliptical profile, over only part of the crack front, is rather unusual. The way the crack front advances into the material away from the free surface shows the increase in restraint into the body of the material and so the likely presence of through thickness stresses. This would suggest the existence of a plane stress / plane strain transition in this material. The crack front turns back towards the initial notch in the centre because the material in the centre of the plaque is tougher because of changes in fibre orientation. This is something not considered above; changes in fibre orientation may well effect the existence of through thickness stresses.

Fig. 11. Fracture Surface Nylon Composite Grade A

Conclusions

Short Fibre Composites with ductile matrices do not appear to undergo plane stress / plane strain transitions. Composites with brittle matrices do undergo such transitions. In general however most of these effects are swamped by changes in fibre orientation with changes in size.

Jc tests appear to work well with these materials. The commonly used blunting line must be discounted because it uses global properties to predict micro-structural effects. The value of Jc appears to be insensitive to changes in temperature for the limited temperature range studied but the slope of the J curve (dJ/da) is not. The value of Jc is also largely independent of specimen size and type at least for the limited number of examples covered.

References

- [1] S. Hashemi and J.G. Williams, *Plastics and Rubber Processing and Applications* 6 (1986) 363 - 375
- [2] B.D. Agarwal, B.S. Patro and P. Kumar. *Eng. Fract. Mech.* 19(1984) 675 - 684
- [3] J.F. Mandell, A.Y. Darwish and F.J. McGarry. *ASTM STP 734*. C.C. Chamis, Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, 1981. pp.73-90
- [4] F.J. McGarry, J.F. Mandell and S.S. Wang. *Polym. Eng. Sci.* 16 (1976) 609 - 614
- [5] K. Friedrich, Report CCM - 80 - 17, Centre for Composite Materials, Univ. of Delaware
- [6] Thanks to K. Vecchio, Lehigh University.